

A STUDY OF ADJUSTMENT OF SCHOOL TEACHERS AT DIFFERENT LEVELS

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Abstract:

The present study aims to investigate the adjustment of school teachers at different levels. Using random sampling technique 290 teachers from the primary, secondary and higher secondary level in different systems of education, namely, government, government aided and private schools are chosen. The adjustment Scale A.K.P. Sinha and R.P. Singh have been used to assess the adjustment for the present study. The data collected is subjected to statistical analysis, namely, mean, standard deviation, 't'- test, 'F'- ratio, Results show that a there is no significant difference found out between the samples of Gender, Type of Management, Level of Teaching, Age, Year of Teaching Experience and Marital Status towards adjustment of school teachers further it shows that there is significant difference between locality of school and type of family towards adjustment of school teachers.

Keys Words: Adjustment & School Teachers

Introduction:

Life is a constant struggle to achieve something or the other, or simply be at peace with oneself. The goals may include being successful in school, maintaining good health, experiencing a happy home life or being successful in a chosen vocation. When the results fall short of expectations or the procedures appear tough, an individual tends to alter his goal, methods or attitudes without causing too much injury to ones' own ego. This constant process of changing oneself to suit the prevailing situation is called Adjustment'. If this process of change results in wholesome and constructive attitudes and behavior, an individual is said to have adjusted well to his environment. However, where such changes result in generation of a feeling of failure or self-pity, or development of negative attitude, the process is called 'maladjustment'.

Adjustment is the behavioral process by which humans and other animals maintain equilibrium among their various needs or between their needs and the obstacles of their environments. The process of adjustment has two main elements: the need of living organism, and the circumstances that influence those needs. These needs may be biogenic, socio genic, personal or communal, or arising from any other conceivable source. On the other hand, the circumstances influencing these needs also can either be inside the individual that influence these needs are his physical and mental states, capacity, attitudes, interests, etc.

Statement of the Research Problem:

The A Study of adjustment of school teachers at different levels has been conducted in order to study.

Population and Sample Characteristics:

The target population for the present study is the school teachers working in different categories of schools following different systems of education at the primary, secondary and higher secondary level. From the target population a sample of 290 working teachers (96 from primary level, 126 from secondary and 68 higher secondary) are chosen.

Instrument:

The research tool used for the present study to analyze the, Adjustment of different level of working teachers is Adjustment Scale A.K.P. Sinha and R.P. Singh.

Methodology:

The sample consisted of 290 working teachers in different level were randomly selected from Tamilnadu. In order to collect data for the study the tool which was constructed and validated by the investigator to assess the Adjustment of different level of working teachers is Adjustment Scale A.K.P. Sinha and R.P. Singh has been adopted by the investigator for the present study. This tool consisted of 60 items under five alternatives such as strongly agree, agree, uncertain, disagree and strongly disagree which was modified and validated. The reliability coefficient was found to be 0.67.

Operational Definition of Term Used:

Adjustment:

Adjustment is process that takes a person to lead a happy and well contented life in society. Adjustment helps in keeping balance between ones way of life according to demand of situation. Adjustment gives strength and ability to bring desirable changes in the conditions of one's environment.

Objectives:

- ✓ To find out if there exists any significant difference between male and female school teachers with respect to their adjustment.

- ✓ To find out if there exists any significant difference between rural and urban of school teachers with respect to their adjustment.
- ✓ To find out whether the significant difference exists among sub samples of type of management with respect to their adjustment of school teachers.
- ✓ To find out whether the significant difference exists among sub samples of level of teaching with respect to their adjustment of school teachers.
- ✓ To find out whether the significant difference exists among sub samples of age with respect to their adjustment of school teachers.
- ✓ To find out whether the significant difference exists among sub samples of years of teaching experience with respect to their adjustment of school teachers.
- ✓ To find out if there exists any significant difference between married and unmarried of school teachers with respect to their adjustment.
- ✓ To find out if there exists any significant difference between nuclear and joint of school teachers with respect to their adjustment.

Hypotheses:

- ✓ There is no significance difference between following sub samples of school teachers regarding their adjustment.
 - Gender : Male/ Female
 - Locality of School : Rural / Urban
 - Type of Management : Government / Aided/ Private
 - Level of Teaching : Primary / Secondary / Hr. Secondary
 - Age : 25 – 35 / 36 – 45 / 46-55
 - Year of Teaching Experience : Below 10 / 11-20 /21 -30 / Above 31
 - Marital Status : Married / Unmarried
 - Type of Family : Nuclear / Joint Family

Analysis of Data:

Gender and Adjustment:

Table 1: Significant of Difference between Adjustment of the Gender towards School Teachers

Gender	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Male	174	39.16	2.53	0.564	NS
Female	116	39.32	2.35		

It is evident from Table 1, the calculated 't' value is 0.564, which is significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis was accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found between male and female school teachers with respect to their adjustment.

Locality of School and Adjustment:

Table 2: Significant of Difference between Adjustment of the Locality of School towards School Teachers

Locality of School	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Rural	215	39.45	2.28	2.643	S
Urban	75	38.58	2.82		

It is evident from Table 2, the calculated 't' value is 2.643, which is significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis was rejected and research hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that there is significant difference found between rural and urban school teachers with respect to their adjustment.

Type of Management and Adjustment:

Table 3: 'F' Values for Adjustment Scores – School Teachers– Based on Type of Management

Type of Management	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Squares	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	18.732	2	9.366	1.548	NS
Within Groups	1736.247	287	6.050		
Total	1754.979	289			

Table 3, the calculated 'F' value is 1.548, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their adjustment of school teachers.

Level of Teaching and Adjustment:

Table 4: 'F' Values for Adjustment Scores – School Teachers – Based on Level of Teaching

Level of Teaching	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Squares	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	15.782	2	7.891	1.302	NS
Within Groups	1739.198	287	6.060		
Total	1754.979	289			

Table 4, the calculated 'F' value is 1.302, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of Level of Teaching with respect to their adjustment of school teachers.

Age and Adjustment:

Table 5: 'F' Values for Adjustment Scores – School Teachers – Based on Age

Age	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	5.762	2	2.881	0.473	NS
Within Groups	1749.217	287	6.095		
Total	1754.979	289			

Table 5, the calculated 'F' value is 0.473, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of age with respect to their adjustment of school teachers.

Year of Teaching Experience and Adjustment:

Table 6: 'F' Values for Adjustment Scores – School Teachers– Based on Year of Teaching Experience

Year of Teaching Experience	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Squares	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	1.267	3	.422	0.069	NS
Within Groups	1753.712	286	6.132		
Total	1754.979	289			

Table 6, the calculated 'F' value is 0.069, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of year of teaching experience with respect to their adjustment of school teachers.

Marital Status and Adjustment:

Table 7: Significant of Difference between Adjustment of the Marital Status towards School Teachers

Marital Status	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Married	175	39.12	2.78	0.868	NS
Unmarried	115	39.38	1.87		

It is evident from Table 7, the calculated 't' value is 0.868, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis was accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is a no significant difference found between married and unmarried family of school teachers with respect to their adjustment.

Type of Family and Adjustment:

Table 8: Significant of Difference between Adjustment of the Type of Family towards School Teachers

Type of Family	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Joint	40	37.95	2.95	3.604	S
Nuclear	250	39.43	2.31		

It is evident from Table 8, the calculated 't' value is 3.604, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis was rejected and research hypothesis is accepted.. It is inferred that there is a significant difference found between nuclear and joint family of school teachers with respect to their adjustment.

Major Findings of the Study:

The present study basically designed to examine the adjustment of school teachers in Vellore District. The major findings drawn from the present study are given below:

- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference found between male and female school teachers with respect to their adjustment.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is significant difference found between rural and urban school teachers with respect to their adjustment.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their adjustment of school teachers.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of Level of Teaching with respect to their adjustment of school teachers.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of age with respect to their adjustment of school teachers.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of year of teaching experience with respect to their adjustment of school teachers.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is a significant difference found between married and unmarried family of school teachers with respect to their adjustment.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is a significant difference found between nuclear and joint family of school teachers with respect to their adjustment.

Recommendations for the Present Study:

- ✓ The present study is confined to 290 school teachers. It is suggested that future researchers may undertake studies with large sample.
- ✓ This study is confined to primary, secondary and higher secondary teachers working in various levels.
- ✓ This study is limited to psychological variables it may be extended to other psychological variables.
- ✓ Similar studies may be conducted in general education from school level to the university level.
- ✓ Similar studies may be conducted in other professional courses like Engineering, Medicine etc.

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